

Research Article

Anti- Atherosclerotic Activity of Salvia Splendens On Triton X- 100 Induced Atherosclerosis in Experimental Animal

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ABSTRACT

Herbal plants contains several bioactive constituents may possess potential cardioprotective effects. The objective for present research work is to investigate herbal medication for atherosclerosis. The attempt is made to investigate this plant with promising effectiveness against atherosclerosis. Therefore the present study is used to evaluate anti-atherosclerotic activity of Salvia splendens in triton x -100 induced atherosclerotic rat model. Atherosclerosis were induced in male wistar rats by intraperitoneal administration of Triton X-100mg/kg body weight for 21 days. The methanolic extract of Salvia splendens leaves (100, 300 mg/kg) administered orally to Triton x- 100 treated rats for next 21 days. Rats were subjected to evaluate general parameter and biochemical parameters. Physical parameters were estimated at 1, 7, 14, 21 days. Biochemical parameters were also estimated in the same intervals by collecting the blood samples from tail vein under mild ether anesthesia. Then the rats were sacrificed on 22nd day, the heart was dissected out for histopathological studies. The elevated serum biochemical parameter such as TC (total cholesterol), LDL (low density lipoprotein), VLDL (very low density lipoprotein), HDL (high densisty lipoprotein, TG (triglyceride) and AI (atherogenic index). Triton X- 100 treated rats were reverted back approximately near to normal after the treatment of Salvia splendens leaves at a doses of 100 and 300 mg/kg. Salvia splendens leaves possess protective action against Triton X- 100 induced atherosclerosis in wistar rats which may be attributed by its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anticoagulant effect.

INTRODUCTION

Atherosclerosis is a long-term disorder characterized by the accumulation of plaque in the

arteries. The primary traditional risk factors for atherosclerosis are genetic disorders, diabetes, smoking cigarettes, dyslipoproteinemia and hypertension.[1]The most prevalent kind of

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cardiovascular disease (CVD), atherosclerosis or coronary artery disease (CAD), is primarily caused by elevated cholesterol levels and inflammation of the major arteries in the heart. Atherosclerosis can ultimately result in its clinical consequences, myocardial infarction (MI), and stroke. Clinically severe atherosclerosis progresses slowly affecting mostly to the elderly patient. Although incidence is on the decline in many nations, it is still the largest cause of death globally. In the intimal space underneath a blood vessel the lipids, inflammatory cells, smooth muscle cells, and necrotic cell debris accumulate and change throughout the course of a lifetime in atherosclerotic lesions. [2] Triton X-100 has been used to induce hyperlipidaemia (a major cause of atherosclerosis) in rats. [4] Triton acts as a surfactant and suppresses the action of lipases to block the uptake of lipoproteins from circulation by extrahepatic tissue, resulting in increased blood lipid concentration. Hyperlipidaemia is characterized by elevated serum total cholesterol, low-density cholesterol, very low-density lipo protein cholesterol, and decreased high-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels. [5] In this research, we aimed to study the mechanism of development of atherosclerosis, including endothelial dysfunction, fatty streak formation, fibrous plaque formation, and plaque rupture. Herbal products are effective against CVD alone or in combination with other drugs, [6] noted that hundreds of plant-based products are traditionally used to treat diseases. However, some of the herbs show side effects that sometimes exceed their benefits. Therefore, impact of herbs on biological mechanisms needs to be investigated. A large number of traditional herbs have been reported, which have efficacy against CVD. Some of the suggested and scientifically proven herbs are *Cynara scolymus* (artichoke), *Allium sativus*-(garlic), *Ginkgo biloba*, *Commiphora mukul*, *Crataegus* species, *Vitis vinifera* (grape), *Crocus sativa* (saffron), and

Camellia sinensis (tea). [6] These herbs exhibit potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, which makes them effective against CVD and associated complications. Chemical analysis of these plant extracts revealed that they contain large number of bioactive phytochemicals, which provides unlimited opportunities for the development of new drugs against several diseases, including CVD. [7] Numerous studies reported that species from the Lamiaceae family have potent cardioprotective effects among various medicinal and aromatic herbs. [8-9] These plants can be used as crude extracts, essential oils (EOs), or active compounds against CVD. [10] It is important to note that the Lamiaceae family of plants contains various classes of bioactive compounds including flavonoids, terpenoids, and alkaloids. This plant family and their active compounds have shown promising cardioprotective activity. One of the most *Salvia* genera, known to act as strong cardioprotective agents, which can notably improve myocardial ischemia in patients with CVDs. [11] *Salvia*, in combination with other herbs, has a more potent effect. For example, *Salvia* and *Astragalus* show a positive synergistic effect and reduce symptoms of hemorrheology in patients with heart failure. [12-13]

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Drugs and Chemicals:

Treatment drug: *Salvia splendens* leaves extract
The leaves of plant were collected from forest region of Amravati district Maharashtra (India). The identification and authentication of plant was done at Department of Botany, Vidyabharati Mahavidyalaya, camp Road Amravati, by Prof. M. U. Ghusde.

Inducing Agent: Triton X-100 (Mfg. By LOBA CHEMIE PVT Limited) purchased from Shree

Ganesh Scientific Syndicate Laboratory, Rajkamal Chauk, Badnera Road, Amravati Dist.: Amravati, Maharashtra- 444601.

Standard drug: Fenofibrate (Mfg. By Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd.) were purchased from Anant medical Agency of Amravati, Maharashtra- 444601

Preparation of Doses: To make 1% of Triton X-100: into the 1 ml of Triton x 100 add it to 99 mL of sterile saline or with distilled water. Injection volume 1 mL per 100 g body weight (adjust as per rat weight). Two different concentrations (100 mg/kg, and 300 mg/kg) of the MESS were prepared by dissolving the extracts in distilled water. All solutions were freshly prepared at the time of administration to the animals. Extract solution, Standard Drug and vehicle (0.9% NaCl) were given orally and inducing drug (Triton X 100 mg/kg) intraperitoneally.

Preparation of plant Extract (Methanolic extract)

The leaves of *Salvia splendens* was processed by washing with clean water, air-drying. Tool consists of several parts including a heat round bottom flask, Soxhlete extractor, and condenser. The solid coarsely powdered roots (250g) were placed in thimble and placed in an extractor. The bottom end of the extractor was connected to a round bottom flask containing a solvent (Methanol 1500ml was chosen as the solvent), and was connected to a reflux condenser. The bottom flask was heated to boil the solvent (methanol), the vapor rises through the branch pipe of the extractor, was condensed and drops in to the thimble and the solvent (methanol) was contacted with the solid for extraction. When the solvent (methanol) surface exceed highest point of the siphon, the solvent containing the extract was return back to the round bottom flask. This cycle

was repeated until the all the material extracted from the solid leaves powder. The Soxhlet extractor can run continuously without any further operation, making it an excellent choice for extracting compounds over hours or even days. Filtration is not required, so it save lot of time, energy and financial inputs. [14] The percentage yield of the extract was calculated and the extract was then subjected to different phytochemical tests.

Experimental animals:

The experiment was performed on Wister rats, 150-250g which was obtained from the animal house of Department of Pharmacology, Vidyabharati college of Pharmacy, Amravati. All the animals were acclimatized to animal house prior to use. They are kept in cage to animal house with 12h light: 12h dark cycle. Animals were fed on pellets and tap water ad libitum. The care and handling of rats were in accordance with the internationally accepted standard guidelines for use of animals (CPCSEA). Permission Registration number - 1504/PO/RE/S/11/CPCSEA and approval for animal studies were obtained from Institutional Animal Committee (LAEC) of Vidyabharati College of Pharmacy, Amravati, and SGB Amravati University.

Experimental Method:

Thirty male wistar rats were selected and divided in to five groups, with six animals in each group. Protocols to assess the protective effects of *S. Splendens* and its isolated Flavonoids and phenolic compound against Triton X- 100 induced atherosclerosis.

Group I (Normal control)

Rats received oral administration of normal saline for 21 days. This group served as a negative control, indicating baseline health without any induced atherosclerosis or treatment effects.

Group II (Toxicant control)

Rats were administered with inducing agent Triton x- 100 intraperitoneal 100 mg /kg of single dose on day 0.

Group III (standard control)

Rats were administered 65 mg/kg body weight Fenofibrate per oral for 21 days with Triton x-100 IP 100mg/kg for 21 days.

Group IV (Low dose test group)

Rats were administered 100 mg/kg body weight Salvia splendens leaves extract orally for 21 days.

Group V (High dose test group)

The rats were administered 300mg/kg body weight Salvia splendens leaves extract orally for 21 days. Triton x- 100 (100 mg/kg) body weight, was administered intraperitoneally to rats in groups 2-6 concomitantly with the above treatment for 21 days. After the last administration, animals were weighed again and sacrificed under light diethyl ether vapour.

Collection of blood samples and organs:

After days of treatment Blood was collected from all the groups in regular intervals of day 1st, 7th, 14th, and 21st through tail vein, under mild ether anesthesia. For serum separation the blood samples were subjected to centrifugation at 4000rpm for 10minutes at 37°C temperature. All the separated serum samples were stored at -200°C temperature until analysis. The serum was separated by micropipettes and it was used for

various biochemical estimations. [15] These estimations were carried out for 4 times in regular time intervals. At the end of the experiment, the animals were sacrificed and the heart dissected out for histopathological evaluation.

Biochemical measurements:

Serum analysis:

Atherosclerosis was assessed by quantifying the serum levels of Total cholesterol (TC), High density lipoproteins (HDL-C), Triglycerides (TGL), Low density lipoproteins (LDL-C), Very low density lipoproteins (VLDL-C) were calculated as per the standard methods.

Calculation of LDL Cholesterol (mg/dl):

$$\text{LDL cholesterol} = \text{Total cholesterol} - (\text{triglycerides}/5) - \text{HDL cholesterol}$$

Calculation of VLDL Cholesterol (mg/dl):

$$\text{VLDL cholesterol} = \text{Triglycerides}/$$

Calculation of Atherogenic Index (AI)

$$\text{AI} = \text{Total serum cholesterol} / \text{Total serum HDL} - \text{Cholesterol}$$

Histopathological examination of heart:

The isolated heart tissue was fixed in 10% formalin solution, embedded in paraffin and cut into semi-thin sections (5- 6 µm). The tissue sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H &E) and observed under light microscopy (40 X).

Statistical analysis:

All data are expressed as mean± SEM (n=6) and analysed with Two-way ANOVA followed by

Tukey's multiple comparisons test (*p < 0.0001) vs. Triton X 100

RESULTS:

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

The extracted materials underwent phytochemical analysis and pharmacological assessment. The extracts underwent first phytochemical analysis to see whether different secondary metabolites including phenolic, alkaloids, Flavonoids, phenols, terpenoids, tannins, and glycosides reagent solvents of analytical quality.

Acute oral toxicity study: In acute toxicity investigations, male healthy rats were employed by OECD norms -425. Acute Toxicity Study:

Table no. 1 Acute Toxicity Study of MESS

Sr.No.	Dose (mg/kg)	Observation
1.	5 mg/kg	No Death
2.	50 mg/kg	No Death
3.	500 mg/kg	No Death
4.	1000 mg/kg	No Death

In above study acute oral toxicity of Leaves of Methanolic Extract of *Salvia splendens* was carried out according to OECD 420 guideline (Acute Oral Toxicity: Fixed Dose procedure). No adverse effect was reported or mortality in albino wistar rats upto 1000 mg/kg of leaves methanolic extracts of *Salvia splendens*. Therefore, for present experimental studies the 1/10th as a low dose and 1/3rd as a high dose.

Estimation of general parameters:

Body weight:

TableNo. 2: Effect of methanolic extract of leaves of *Salvia splendens* (MESS) on the Body weight in Triton X 100 induced Atherosclerosis

GROUPS	Day 1	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21
Control	177.500±8.34	190.500±8.66	199.16±8.604	213.33±9.08
Triton-X 100 (100mg/kg)	176.667±6.67	254.883±2.587	282.50±4.425	343.333±8.33
Standard (fenofibrate-65mg/kg)	174.167±6.90*	215.00±1.238*	198.33±0.919*	187.17±1.62*
Test-1(MESS-100mg/kg)	176.584±3.05*	238.167±2.272*	238.167±2.272*	204.83±1.86*
Test-2 (MESS-300mg/kg)	175.333±6.25*	222.500±1.118*	105.833±1.447*	196.33±0.71*

All data are expressed as mean± SEM (n=6) and analysed with Two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test (*p < 0.0001) vs. Triton X 100 (100 mg/kg).

Estimation of serum biochemical parameter:

Group I: Control

Table no. 3: Lipid profile parameter in control group

Time Interval	TC	LDL-C	VLDLC	HDL-C	TGL	AI
Day 1	84.945±0.79	41.809±0.72	11.157±0.12	41.960±1.46	86.199±0.79	1.54±0.03
Day 7	86.696±1.46*	42.576±0.46*	11.073±0.17*	42.016±1.42*	86.243±1.17*	1.53±0.23*
Day 14	86.551±1.17*	44.860±0.43*	10.389±0.18*	41.080±1.48*	85.561±1.14*	1.6±0.10*
Day 21	84.95±1.48*	44.686±0.36*	11.037±0.19*	42.391±1.33*	84.495±0.75*	1.26±0.25*

Group II: Negative control:

Table no. 4: Effect of Triton X-100 (100mg/kg) on the Lipid profile.

Time Interval	TC	LDL-C	VLDLC	HDL-C	TGL	AI
Day 1	81.893±0.66	43.878±1.89	11.210±0.26	41.699±1.58	86.642±0.72	1.62±0.13
Day 7	206.14±0.63*	124.88±0.48*	34.258±0.13*	31.570±1.23*	294.56±0.63*	4.03±0.2*
Day 14	220.187±0.73*	138.17±2.27*	37.546±0.26*	28.447±0.79*	319.767±3.8*	4.27±0.29*
Day 21	222.89±0.35*	142.74±2.14*	41.892±0.30*	26.261±0.57*	335.629±2.9*	4.82±0.70*

Group III: Standard:**Table no. 5: Effect of Fenofibrate (65 mg/kg) on the Lipid profile**

Time Interval	TC	LDL-C	VLDLC	HDL-C	TGL	AI
Day 1	86.662±1.58	45.056±0.61	12.158±0.38	42.076±1.87	87.09±0.672	1.72±0.01
Day 7	140.41±0.38*	79.359±0.71*	25.427±0.27*	46.657±0.91*	201.62±1.31*	2.13±0.05*
Day 14	107.79±0.04*	64.631±0.31*	17.405±0.08*	51.997±0.48*	137.85±0.22*	1.78±0.04*
Day 21	94.591±0.01*	58.160±0.39*	12.977±0.10*	57.58±0.27*	108.47±0.25*	1.50±0.06*

Group IV: Test 1**Table no. 6: Effect of MESS 100 mg/kg on the Lipid profile.**

Time Interval	TC	LDL-C	VLDLC	HDL-C	TGL	AI
Day 1	85.827±0.19	43.377±1.25	11.437±0.22	42.574±2.85	87.238±1.10	1.65±0.16
Day 7	170.114±1.10*	91.225±0.87*	30.365±0.19*	44.55±0.72*	225.959±0.95*	3.88±0.09*
Day 14	134.413±0.09*	80.235±1.06*	26.455±0.24*	46.198±1.21*	174.477±1.02*	2.13±0.46*
Day 21	113.51±0.09*	75.450±1.36*	23.212±0.26*	48.643±1.13*	145.122±1.18*	1.74±0.09*

Group V: Test 2**Table no. 7: Effect of MESS 300 mg/kg on the Lipid profile**

Time Interval	TC	LDL-C	VLDLC	HDL-C	TGL	AI
Day 1	86.612±.015	43.6305±1.05	11.038±0.25	41.668±1.53	86.476.88	1.69±0.06
Day 7	160.09±1.53*	83.533±2.08*	27.635±0.15*	44.425±1.53*	209.97±2.20*	2.94±0.04*
Day 14	120.225±2.0*	71.095±0.62*	21.526±0.17*	49.716±1.09*	148.257±1.57*	2.11±0.05*
Day 21	97.957±1.57*	53.634±1.03*	15.543±0.10*	53.735±0.35*	117.97±0.68*	1.53±0.05*

All data are expressed as mean± SEM (n=6) and analysed with Two-way ANOVA followed by

Tukey's multiple comparisons test *(p < 0.0001) vs. Triton X 100

The research finding from the study graphical representation of TC, LDL, VLDL and TG all shows biochemical parameter significantly decrease and Graph of HDL shows significantly increase by the oral consumption of extract, especially at the prescribed dosages of 100mg/kg and 300mg/kg. This result may ultimately imply a potent activity against atherosclerosis. Such outcomes underscore the extract may be potential effect and mechanism and shows significantly increase the value of HDL which indicate that improving the biological activity.

Results of Histopathology:

A)

B)

C)

D)

E)

A) Normal Control group:

Shows the cross section of the heart of the sham group stained with haematoxylin and eosin. Section of heart shows no fatty changes with normal tissue architecture, multiple peripheral nuclei, and regular morphology of myocardial cell membrane.

B) Inducing group Triton X 100 (100mg/kg):

Shows the cross section of the heart of the negative control group stained with haematoxylin and eosin. Section heart shows alteration in tissue

architecture and focal fatty infiltration in myocardial cells.

C) Standard group (Fenofibrate 65mg/kg):

Shows the cross section of the heart of standard control group stained with haematoxylin and eosin. Section of heart shows restored tissue and myocardial architectures.

D) Treatment group MESS 100mg/kg (Methanolic extract *Salvia splendens*):

Shows the cross section of the heart of 100 mg/kg bw group stained with haematoxylin and eosin. Section heart shows focal fatty infiltration in myocardial cells.

E) Treatment group MESS 300mg/kg (Methanolic extract *Salvia splendens*):

Shows the cross section of the heart of the 300 mg/kg bw group stained with haematoxylin and eosin. Heart shows positive cardiomyocytes restoration with very mild fatty infiltration.

DISSCUSION:

The current study was designed to assess the effect of MESS against Triton X-100-induced atherosclerosis in rats. Triton X-100 is reported to block the clearance of TG-rich lipoproteins and produces acute hyperlipidemia and atherosclerosis in animal models. [16-18] Plasma TG and cholesterol levels were elevated due to Triton X-100 injection as an increase of VLDL secretion by the liver, followed by reduction of VLDL and LDL catabolism. In the present study, Triton X-100 significantly increased the serum TC, LDL-C, VLDL-C, TGs, AI and decreased HDL-C levels as also reported in a previous study. [19-20] Triton X-100 inhibits lipoprotein lipase, the enzyme responsible for hydrolyzing triglycerides in chylomicrons and very low-density lipoproteins

(VLDL). This inhibition results in accumulation of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins in the plasma Blocking Hepatic Uptake of Lipoproteins. This leads to elevated levels of plasma lipids, particularly cholesterol and triglycerides. Rapid Induction of Hyperlipidemia and atherosclerosis by intraperitoneal or intravenous administration, Triton X-100 causes acute hyperlipidemia within a few hours depending on the dose and species used. Oxidative Stress and endothelial dysfunction causes excessive lipoproteins in circulation can become oxidized, contributing to oxidative stress. Oxidized LDL promotes endothelial injury, inflammation, and foam cell formation, which are key steps in atherogenesis. Triton X-100 models are typically used for acute hyperlipidemia, repeated or sustained exposure may contribute to early atherosclerotic changes, especially in combination with a high-fat diet or genetic susceptibility result atherosclerotic lesion formation (In Long-Term Use). *Salvia splendens* contains several bioactive constituents may possess potential cardioprotective effects. Among these, rosmarinic acid, a phenolic acid, plays a key role due to its strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. It scavenges reactive oxygen species (ROS) and helps protect the vascular endothelium from oxidative damage. Luteolin, a flavonoid, exhibits both anti-inflammatory and vasodilatory effects by inhibiting the NF- κ B pathway and enhancing nitric oxide (NO) production, which contributes to improved vascular function. [21-22] Another important flavonoid, apigenin, functions as an antioxidant and anti-apoptotic agent, primarily by reducing oxidative stress in cardiomyocytes and helping to maintain cellular integrity under stress conditions. Additionally, *Salvia splendens* has been reported to contain salvianolic acid-like polyphenols, which are known to improve endothelial function. These compounds act by promoting endothelial nitric oxide synthase

(eNOS) activity and inhibiting platelet aggregation, both of which are crucial for maintaining vascular health and preventing thrombosis. Ursolic acid, a triterpenoid also found in the plant, exhibits anti-hyperlipidemic and anti-atherosclerotic activities by lowering LDL cholesterol levels and inhibiting the formation of foam cells, which are central to plaque formation in atherosclerosis. Lastly, though less confirmed in *Salvia splendens* tanshinone-like diterpenes may contribute to cardioprotection by improving mitochondrial function and reducing infarct size during ischemic events. Together, these compounds highlight the potential of *Salvia splendens* as a source of natural agents for cardiovascular protection. In the current study, MESS was able to reverse the Triton X-100-induced levels of serum TC, LDL-C, VLDL-C, TG and decreased the level of HDL-C toward normal limits. The effects of MESS on the markers of atherosclerosis were comparable to Fenofibrate 65 mg/kg, which is mostly prescribed as a standard antihyperlipidemic and anti-atherosclerotic drug. Thus, based on the markers of atherosclerosis, it may be concluded from the present study that MESS may inhibit the synthesis of cholesterol via the mevalonate pathway, and its efficacy was mildly similar to fenofibrate. In the present study, it was established that AI increased in Triton X-100-administered rats as reported in a previous study. AI which is a measure of the extent of atherosclerotic lesion, was significantly reduced by the oral treatment of MESS and Fenofibrate, thus findings shows that pretreatment with both doses of MESS showed decreased AI. Reactive oxygen species are responsible for causing atherosclerosis. Lipid peroxidation induced by reactive oxygen species is a key factor for atherosclerosis. In the present study, there was a significant increase in the levels of lipid peroxide in the liver tissue. MESS (100 mg/kg) significant decrease in the levels of lipid peroxide. The Triton

X-100-treated animals were under severe stress as it was shown by the reduction in liver enzymes and markers of oxidative stress. One study reported that fenofibrate reduced the formation of free radicals in vitro, lipid peroxides, and elevated antioxidant enzymes, thus demonstrating antioxidant effects in hyperlipidemic rat. [23-27] The levels of antioxidant enzymes, such as catalase and SOD, are decreased during cellular inflammation. These enzymes remove oxygen free radicals, thus decreasing inflammatory conditions. We observed that MESS treatment increased the SOD levels more than the control group. A similar pattern of observation with fenofibrate treatment resulted in increased SOD levels more than the vehicle control group. The reason for such effect may be the system was under severe stress, and some compensatory mechanisms may be operative to detoxify the production of reactive oxygen species. While the reason for such an effect observed by MESS is not clear, one possible explanation for an insignificant reduction could be due to a delayed decline of such antioxidant enzymes follow treatment with MESS. Histopathological studies are the most precise evidence for the protective effect of drug as protectants. Simultaneous treatment of MESS with Triton X-100 exhibits less damage to the endothelial cells as compared with rats treated with Triton X-100 alone. The Triton X-100-treated group showed inflammatory cells of inflammation, apoptosis, and proliferation of fibrous connective tissue. Moreover, the MESS- treated group showed less proliferation of endothelial cells in histopathological examinations. MESS was able to showed beneficial effects by maintaining the normal architecture of the heart tissues, which was altered in atherosclerosis as evidenced by histopathological studies. Almost negligible damage to a few endothelial cells was observed in MESS-treated rats. The results of a histopathological study further support the results

of biochemical parameters. Thus, the histopathological evidences again confirm the cardioprotective and anti- atherosclerotic effects of MESS. Further research is needed to confirm the molecular pathways and potential therapeutic use of MESS in atherosclerosis in different animal models with multiple doses.

CONCLUSION:

The above data suggest that *Salvia splendens* leaves extract possess weight reduction properties with no interference with inflammation. The findings of the study ensure that *Salvia splendens* leaves extract effectively able to reduce the serum lipids like LDL-C, TC, TGL, VLDL-C, AI and significant increase in HDL-C. It can be concluded that *Salvia splendens* leaves extract has a potential role in suppressing triton X induced atherosclerosis. Further investigation is needed to confirm the anti-atherosclerotic of *Salvia splendens* clinically. While some of these compounds are better studied in related *Salvia* species, their presence in *S. splendens* suggests that the plant may serve as a valuable natural source for developing therapeutic agents against cardiovascular diseases, particularly atherosclerosis. Further pharmacological and clinical studies are warranted to fully validate and explore its therapeutic efficacy.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVE:

Research on the anti- atherosclerotic activity of *Salvia splendens* is still in its early stages. Preclinical studies using animal models have shown promising results, indicating that extracts of *Salvia splendens* can mitigate the atherosclerotic activity of triton X 100 For example, studies have demonstrated reduction in TC, LDL, VLDL, TGL and increasing HDL parameter. Histopathological improvements in heart tissue. However, more research is needed to

fully understand the mechanisms involved and to establish the efficacy and safety of *Salvia splendens* in humans. Future research should focus on:

- Conducting well-designed clinical trials to confirm the anti- atherosclerotic effects of *Salvia splendens* in patients undergoing atherosclerosis.
- Determining the optimal dosage and form of *Salvia splendens* for anti- atherosclerotic effects.
- Further elucidating the molecular pathways through which *Salvia splendens* exerts its protective effects.
- Exploring potential synergistic effects of combining *Salvia splendens*.with other cardioprotective agent or standard treatments to enhance overall heart protection.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST : We declared that we have no conflict of interest

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